

FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY, TEACHING METHODS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the methodology of foreign language teaching, the history of its development as a science, the types of modern methods used in foreign language teaching methods and their use.*

Keywords: *methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, competencies, didactics, intercultural communication.*

МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ, МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается методика обучения иностранному языку, история его развития как науки, виды современных методов, применяемых в методике обучения иностранному языку и их применение.*

Ключевые слова: *методика, инновация, иностранный язык, коммуникация, умения, компетенции, дидактика, межкультурная коммуникация.*

INTRODUCTION

Modern educational development has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative - means "introduction (dissemination) of innovation" in English. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American researcher E. Rogers. It is an innovation process studied the classification of participants, their attitude to the news, etc. The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

"Innovation" means a tool, new method, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is a process that develops according to certain stages of education. The development of world science is growing and developing day by day. It was this positive development that affected our country as well. Advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. As a result of this, our President named this year as "Year of Youth Support and Public Health", which increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. It would not be a mistake to say that the wide application of advanced, modern innovative technologies in the field of education has opened the door to many opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages.

The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methodology were expressed. One of these views belongs to academician L.V. Shcherba. In his opinion, although the methodology of teaching any subject is a subject, it is not considered a theoretical subject. It solves practical issues. In particular, the methodology of foreign language teaching does not rely only on psychological evidence, but is based on general and specific linguistic studies. If linguistics deals with the origin and laws of movement of language phenomena, the methodology answers the question of what should be done in order to use the necessary language phenomenon in practice based on these laws. The most valuable books on methodology are also written by linguists. These include G. Suit, one of the 19th century phonetists and a great English linguist, O. Yesperson, who is considered the most original phonetist and theoretical linguist in England at the end of the 19th and the beginning of

the 20th century, the 19th century among the most prominent French linguists at the end and beginning of the 20th century are F. Bruns and Bréal, a prominent Anglicist and famous phonetician V. Fyodor, and others. Academician L.V. Shcherba and his mentor, the great linguist scientist I.A. Baudouin-de-Courtone and their students dealt with the issue of language teaching methodology in Russia. Psychologists have a different attitude to the methodology of foreign language teaching. Professor V.A. Artemov made a valuable comment about the relationship between methodology and psychology. In his opinion, psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology studies how the teacher conducts the lesson. Psychology deals with how students learn this subject. However, this opinion cannot be fully agreed. Because the teacher in the process of teaching, and the student in the period of mastering, experience certain mental processes and states, whether they want to or not, they face and are influenced by the laws of psychology.

RESULTS

Method without translation. Various forms of this method are known historically. They can be divided into two large groups: natural and correct methods. Learning a foreign language in a natural way should be similar to the conditions of acquiring the mother tongue. The main goal of the method is the idea that by learning to speak a foreign language, it is possible to learn to read and write. The most important of the principles included in the natural method is to create a language environment. Various approaches have appeared in the practical application of the advanced methodical principles. This can be clearly seen in the creative activity of the method exponents.

The new interpretation of the purpose of foreign language education was mainly based on the results of pragmatic linguistics research. This field of linguistics interprets language as a field of human activity rather than a system of linguistic forms. In the field of foreign language education, since the beginning of the 70s, a set of new conclusions has led to intense discussions in the field of educational goal setting. New curricula were adopted, which set the main directions of foreign language education, with the goal of "teaching students to communicate", "Befaeigung zur Kommunikation" (communicative Kompetenz). In the 70s, the "communicative method" was proven in several stages after a series of attempts. In this way, the science of methodology was developing. We cannot master any foreign language without a deep study of its methodology. The method of "communicative didactics" is also considered important in the methodology of foreign language teaching. Communicative didactics includes the following.

DISCUSSION

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline, in which a person undergoes complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology.

CONCLUSIONS

Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative didactic method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method. All three methods are closely

related and complement each other. Since the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, it is based on communicativeness during foreign language learning and the method of communicative didactics is created.

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